

SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES EMIGRATION IN ARMENIA**Ruzanna S. Yepiskoposyan***Faculty of Sociology, Yerevan State University***Abstract**

The article presents a sociological overview of the reasons for emigration in Armenia, assessing the various factors influencing the decision of citizens to leave their homeland. The article analyzes general emigration trends emanating from historical roots, as well as specific factors associated with modern Armenian reality. The article covers the issue of emigration in Armenia while highlighting the research done on this issue by well-known sociologists. It also looks at the country's current emigration issue.

Keywords: emigration, political emigration, economic emigration.

Introduction

Armenia has always piqued curiosity among both its citizens and the global community due to its rich history and cultural heritage. But in recent years, emigration has sharply increased as more Armenians leave their country in search of better employment prospects, better educational possibilities, or political stability.

Between 740,000 and 1,300,000 people departed Armenia between 1988 and 2005. The economic downturn that engulfed the 1990s was a major factor in the emigration of 125,000 refugees and internally displaced people. Furthermore, as a result of many natural and man-made disasters, including the 1988 Spitak earthquake, 192,000 Armenians were internally displaced.

Emigration from Armenia has had a profound impact on the country's economic, political, and socio-cultural dynamics. This article aims to analyze different aspects of emigration from Armenia. It begins with an overview of the types of emigration and its historical roots. Subsequently, it delves into sociological research conducted on this subject.

The paper also discusses Armenia's current emigration issue, outlining patterns and offering statistical information. It also examines the societal, political, and economic issues that drive Armenians to emigrate. Finally, a full assessment of the effects of immigration on the nation's economy and demographics is made. Finally, we will evaluate the measures and programs taken by the Armenian government and local organizations to mitigate emigration trends. Analyzing emigration in Armenia is important for understanding the challenges the country faces and developing strategies

1. Emigration in general**1.1. Types of emigration: Overview of the main types of emigration**

The study of emigration necessitates classifying it into various forms based on the factors that cause people to leave their own country. The three main categories of emigration - economic, political, and educational, will be covered in this section of the essay.

Economic emigration:

One of the most common types of migration is economic emigration. People decide to emigrate in search of better living and employment prospects. This kind of emigration can be caused by a number of circumstances.

High unemployment: Firstly, high unemployment rates in certain countries push citizens to seek employment abroad, where job opportunities are more abundant.

Low income: Additionally, individuals may decide to emigrate if the income in their home country is insufficient to maintain a decent standard of living or meet their basic needs. They hope to find better-paying jobs in other countries.

Economic crises: Economic crises, inflation and financial difficulties can encourage people to seek stability and opportunity abroad.

Political emigration:

Political emigration involves the flight of citizens due to political instability, persecution or human rights violations in their home country. The main reasons for political emigration may be:

- **Political Persecution:** Citizens may face harassment, threats, or violence from government or political organizations.
- **Dictatorship and authoritarianism:** The desire to live in a country with democratic institutions can encourage citizens to leave authoritarian regimes.
- **Political Refugees:** People may become political refugees when their life or freedom is threatened due to political conflicts or wars.

Educational emigration:

Individuals who go abroad for education, study or scientific research are referred to as educational "emigration".

- This type of emigration could be caused by any of the following factors: The ability to emigrate provides citizens with better access to higher education, which they may not have in their home country.
- **Scientific Research:** Scientists and researchers may emigrate to collaborate with international scientific organizations or to access advanced research laboratories and libraries.
- Emigration for educational or study purposes also fosters cultural exchange and a variety of knowledge across different regions.

The study of emigration provides insight into the motives of individuals who migrate and offers suggestions on how to develop policies that cater to their preferences. Below, we will examine the most common types of emigration in Armenia and the factors that influence their decision to do so.

1.2. Historical roots

The emigration pattern in Armenia is heavily influenced by historical events. The Armenian

Genocide in 1915 and the Soviet era, which saw Armenia become part of the USSR, were both significant periods for emigration from Armenia.

Armenian Genocide of 1915:

Armenians were subjected to the Armenian Genocide, which was carried out during World War I and led by the Ottoman Empire in modern Turkey. Millions of Armenian casualties followed, as well as many people fleeing violence and persecution. The impact of this historical event on Armenians' consciousness was profound and played a crucial role in the significant exodus from their homeland.

- The disappearance of cultural centers and historical areas during the genocide resulted in a large number of Armenians seeking refuge abroad.

- Following the Genocide, an Armenian diaspora was formed worldwide, and emigrants played a crucial role in shaping the Armenianist Armenian culture/community outside Armenia.

Soviet period:

In 1920, Armenia joined the USSR and became a union republic. During Soviet rule, changes occurred that also affected emigration from Armenia.

- The industrialization and collectivization of agriculture during the Soviet era brought about changes in Armenian society and economic structure.
- Some people decided to leave in search of better opportunities.
- At different times of Soviet power, repression and mass deportation occurred, which may cause individuals who were breaking political or ideological rules to leave their homeland.

- The Soviet Union allowed Armenian citizens to work and reside in other areas of the USSR, which facilitated population movements.

- Emigration from Armenia has been shaped by these historical events, and their impact is still felt in the country today. Rephrase
- The subsequent sections of the article will examine the factors that are prompting Armenian emigration and their impact on the country and its diaspora.

These historical occurrences significantly influenced the development of the emigration trend from Armenia and still have an impact on the country's current emigration status today. In the parts that follow, we'll examine the reasons behind Armenian emigration right now as well as the effects it has on both the nation and the diaspora.

1.3. Sociologists and Research:

The study of the phenomenon of emigration and its sociological aspects has become the object of interest of many researchers. The reasons, processes, and effects of emigration have been extensively studied by a number of renowned sociologists. Among them are Ravenstein Emigration and Douglas Massey, whose theories and studies have significantly influenced the area of emigration sociology.

Ravenstein Emigration:

Emigration American sociologist and demographer Ravenstein is well known for his contributions to

the study of immigration and emigration in the country. His writings, such as *Emigration and Cultural Change*, emphasize the significance of sociocultural elements in the emigration and immigrant integration processes.

- **Acculturation and Assimilation:** The idea of acculturation and assimilation was created by Ravenstein, and it describes how immigrants adjust to a new culture and assimilate into the receiving society. He emphasized that this process is reciprocal and can affect both immigrants and the society into which they arrive.

- **Emigration and sociocultural change:** Ravenstein also examined how emigration affects sociocultural change in both the sending and destination countries. He paid attention to the interaction of cultures and the transformation of identity in the context of emigration.

Douglas Massey:

American sociologist and demographer Douglas Massey made important contributions to the research on immigration and emigration as well. His thoughts and research primarily analyze long-term trends in migratory dynamics and their societal ramifications.

- **World Systems Theory:** Massey developed world systems theory, which explains migration as a consequence of global economic and political changes. He examined how world systems influence migration and shape inequalities in the world.

- **Demography and Migration:** Massey has also studied the relationship between migration and demography, examining how migration impacts population trends and demographic shifts in both sending and receiving nations.

Together, the works of Ravenstein and Massey illustrate the complexity of emigration processes and contribute to the development of a theoretical framework for comprehending these phenomena. Additionally, their research aids in the creation of doable strategies for controlling and regulating immigration and emigration in the contemporary world.

2. Emigration in Armenia

2.1.. Current situation.

The current emigration situation in Armenia reflects various factors, influencing the decision of citizens to leave their homeland. To understand the current situation, we will analyze statistical data and identify the main trends.

Statistical data:

Let's start by examining the data presented by official sources and international organizations:

1. **Total number of emigrants:** According to reports, Armenians are emigrating in increasing numbers. Since Armenia's independence in 1991, a sizeable portion of the population has left the country. According to current estimates, there are more Armenians living abroad than there are in Armenia itself.

2. **Main migration routes:** Armenians primarily migrate to Russia, the United States, France, Germany, and other nations where there is a sizable Armenian diaspora. Russia remains one of the largest attractive labor markets for Armenian citizens due to historical ties and close geographic proximity.

3. **Reasons for Migration:** Economic concerns, such as low earnings, high unemployment, and a lack of employment possibilities, frequently influence emigration from Armenia. The decision to immigrate may also be influenced by political and sociological factors.

Trends:

Modern trends in Armenian emigration include the following:

1. **Youth emigration:** One noticeable trend is the emigration of young people, including university graduates. The lack of prospects in Armenia and the desire to get education or work experience abroad encourage young people to migrate.

2. **Family emigration:** Some families choose to leave their country of origin in order to better their quality of life and give their children a brighter future.

3. **Diaspora influence:** The Armenian diaspora continues to be crucial in helping emigrants and giving them chances to adapt in new societies.

4. **Emigration management:** To control emigration and promote Armenians' return to their country of origin, the government of Armenia is creating policies and initiatives.

An examination of Armenia's present emigration scenario reveals the necessity of developing both domestic and international policies and initiatives to support the Armenian diaspora. We will examine the causes of emigration and its societal repercussions in Armenia in greater detail in the parts that follow.

2.2. Reasons for emigration:

The reasons prompting Armenian citizens to emigrate are diverse and related to economic, political and sociocultural aspects. To understand the motivation of emigrants from Armenia, let's consider these factors in more detail:

Economic forces:

1. **Low income:** One of the main economic motives for emigration is insufficiently high wages and the low standard of living in Armenia. People who are struggling financially can decide to look for employment abroad, where the opportunities may be more lucrative.

2. **Unemployment:** Armenia has a high unemployment rate, making it difficult for many people to find employment and support their families. Emigration can be a way to escape unemployment.

3. **Economic prospects:** Lack of economic prospects and business opportunities may cause entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial - spirited citizens to consider emigration as a way to develop their businesses.

Political factors:

1. **Political instability:** Periodic political crises and instability in Armenia can create uncertainty and anxiety among citizens. Some people might choose to leave the nation in order to avoid political hazards.

2. **Corruption and ineffective government:** Corruption and ineffective administration can limit citizens' chances and even make them feel powerless in the face of the state.

Sociocultural factors:

1. **Education and career:** Some Armenians may emigrate for better education or career development in more developed countries.

2. **Family connections:** Family separation can be a motivation for emigration, with part of the family leaving to support loved ones abroad.

3. **Cultural considerations:** Deciding to emigrate can also be influenced by cultural factors, such as a desire to live in a more accepting or globalized culture.

It should be noted that these factors can interact and have a joint impact on the decision of Armenian citizens to emigrate. In addition, many Armenian emigrants have mixed motives that include both economic and sociocultural or political aspects. Understanding these motivations is an important part of developing policies and programs to manage emigration and ensure sustainable development in a country.

2.3. Consequences for the country:

Emigration from Armenia has a significant impact on the country, leaving its mark on the economic and demographic levels. Let's look at the key implications for Armenia:

Economic consequences:

1. **Labor outflow:** Emigration leads to an outflow of labor, including highly qualified specialists. Due to potential staffing shortages, this can have a detrimental effect on the nation's economic progress.

2. **Sending money transfers:** Many Armenian emigrants send money to their families in Armenia. These transfers, or remittances, are crucial to a nation's economy and can make up a sizeable amount of GDP.

3. **Loss of intellectual capital:** The emigration of scientists, specialists and innovators can lead to a loss of intellectual capital and research potential, which can slow down innovative growth and the development of science and technology in the country.

4. **Decrease in domestic consumer demand:** A decline in population and purchasing power may reduce domestic consumer demand, which could impact local markets and businesses.

Demographic implications:

1. **Population decline:** Emigration leads to a decrease in the population of Armenia. This may have an impact on the demographic structure of the country and cause demographic challenges such as an aging population.

2. **Family divisions:** Emigration can lead to family separation, with some family members remaining in Armenia while others move abroad. This can influence family structure and sociocultural aspects of life.

3. **Change in ethnic structure:** In some cases, emigration can affect the ethnic structure of a country, as some ethnic groups may be more inclined to emigrate.

4. **The level of education:** Emigration can affect the level of education in a country, as some young people may decide to go abroad for education and not return after completing their studies.

Overall, emigration has a complex impact on Armenia, mixing economic and demographic consequences. It is important for the country to develop strat-

egies and policies that can manage these impacts, including facilitating the return of emigrants, attracting investment and developing the economy, and supporting families remaining in Armenia.

2.4. Fight against emigration:

Armenia faces the challenge of maintaining its population and mitigating emigration trends. In response to these challenges, the Armenian government and local organizations are taking a number of measures and programs:

1. Economic measures:

- Job creation: The Government of Armenia is actively working to create new jobs and development of the business environment. This includes supporting start-ups, investing in infrastructure and facilitating business procedures.

- Support for SMEs: Measures aimed at supporting SMEs can create jobs and increase economic opportunities for citizens, which may reduce their motivation to emigrate.

2. Educational programs:

- Educational development: Investments in the education system, including higher education levels, can make Armenia more attractive to young people seeking quality education.

- Exchange Programs: Exchange programs and scholarships abroad can provide youth with the opportunity to gain international experience and education without leaving the country.

3. Social programs:

- Social support: The government provides various types of social support, including child subsidies and financial assistance for low-income families.

- Return programs: Some programs facilitate the return of Armenian emigrants by providing benefits and assistance in returning and adapting to the country.

4. Measures to strengthen ties with the diaspora:

- Cooperation with the Armenian diaspora: The government actively cooperates with the Armenian diaspora, including on issues of investment and support for projects in Armenia.

- Hosting cultural events: Organizing cultural events and festivals can help strengthen ties with the Armenian diaspora and stimulate interest in their home country.

It should be noted that the effectiveness of these measures and programs may vary, and the fight against emigration requires a comprehensive and long-term approach. It is important to take into account the changing circumstances and needs of citizens in order to develop effective strategies to mitigate emigration trends and strengthen the development of Armenia.

Conclusion

Emigration in Armenia is a complex social and economic phenomenon that has a profound impact on the country. Having considered various aspects of emigration, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. **Multifaceted reasons:** Emigration from Armenia is due to many factors, including economic, political and sociocultural aspects. Low incomes, high unemployment, political instability and the desire to get a

better education are all motives that encourage citizens to emigrate.

2. **Complex consequences:** Emigration has a variety of impacts on Armenia. Population decline, labor outmigration and loss of intellectual capital pose significant challenges. However, remittances from Armenian emigrants, support from the diaspora, and educational opportunities abroad can provide benefits.

3. **Fight against emigration:** The Armenian government and local organizations are taking measures and programs to mitigate emigration trends. These measures include job creation, support for small and medium-sized businesses, education development and social programs. Strengthening ties with the Armenian diaspora is also important.

4. **The need for sustainable development:** To successfully combat emigration and ensure sustainable development of Armenia, a long-term vision and an integrated approach are needed. Effective measures must take into account the changing circumstances and needs of citizens.

Overall, emigration remains an important topic for Armenia, and solving this problem requires joint efforts on the part of the state, local organizations and citizens. With the right strategy and implementation of measures, emigration trends can be mitigated and conditions for the prosperity and development of the country can be created.

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